

Search for New Hypoglycemic Agents. Part V: 1-(Thiadiazolyl-5-(Substituted Benzylidene) Hydantoin)s and 1-(*p*-Chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-Substituted Barbituric Acids

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Synthesis of some new 1-(5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-5-(substituted benzylidene) hydantoin)s and 1-(*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-alkyl/aryl/cyclo-hexyl barbituric acids have been described. Three of these barbituric acids caused reduction in blood sugar upto 33% whereas hydantoin)s showed insignificant reduction when screened in rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg.

ROY and coworkers¹ have reported that a few substituted hydantoates and hydantoin)s exhibited hypoglycemic activity of an order equal to that of carbutamide. The oral hypoglycemic action of some thiadiazole derivatives^{2,3,4} has long been known. Anderson⁵ has also pointed that the hypoglycemic activity of Hypoglycin A is owing to the presence of an ethylenic linkage in it. In view of these findings, it was considered desirable to synthesise the above hydantoin)s containing thiadiazole moiety as well as ethylenic linkage.

Further, sulphonyl ureas^{6,7,8} especially tolbutamide and Chlorpropamide (1-*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl-3-*n*-propyl-urea) are most widely used in the therapy of diabetes. Deshpande *et al.*⁹ have recently reported that some 1-(*p* toluenesulphonyl)-3-alkyl or aryl barbituric acids showed significant lowering in blood sugar in fasted albino rats. This stimulated our interest to cyclise 1-(*p*-chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-substituted ureas with malonyl chloride to produce the title barbituric acids in order to test the idea whether the cyclisation of the former results in the enhancement of the activity.

5-Alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl urea, prepared by the reaction of 5-alkyl-2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole¹⁰ with potassium cyanate, on condensation with

chloroacetic acid in anhydrous pyridine gave 1-(5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)hydantoin)s. The latter were further reacted with different substituted benzaldehydes to obtain 1-(5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-5-(substituted benzylidene) hydantoin)s.

1-(*p*-Chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-substituted urea^{11,12,13} was refluxed with malonyl chloride¹⁴ in the presence of chloroform to give the desired barbituric acid derivatives.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. 5-Alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl ureas were prepared according to the method reported earlier¹⁰.

1-(5-Alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) hydantoin)s: On warming a mixture of 5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl urea (0.01 mol) and chloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) in anhydrous pyridine (20 ml) on a water bath, an exothermic reaction ensued. When this reaction had subsided, the mixture was cooled, when a viscous liquid was obtained 20 ml of absolute alcohol was added to this liquid and the resulting mixture was refluxed for one hr. On subsequent cooling, a crystalline solid separated out. It was filtered and recrystallised from ethyl acetate.

The hydantoin)s thus obtained are listed in Table 1.

TABLE—1. 1-(5-ALKYL-1,3,4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL) HYDANTOINS

S. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Percentage of nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	268	50	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	28.00	28.28
2.	C ₆ H ₅	153	62	C ₇ H ₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	26.12	26.42
3.	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₇	174-6	65	C ₈ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	25.14	24.78

1-(5-Alkyl-1, 3, 4-thiadiazol-2-yl)-5-(substituted benzylidene) hydantoin: A mixture consisting of 1-(5-alkyl-1, 3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) hydantoin (0.01 mol), the appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol), glacial acetic acid (20 ml), fused sodium acetate (1 gm) and a few drops of acetic anhydride was refluxed in an oil bath at 140-150° for 8 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the product obtained was filtered and recrystallised from n-hexane or ethyl acetate (Table 2).

1-(p-Chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-alkyl|aryl|cyclohexyl-barbituric acids: Malonyl chloride (0.01 mol), 1-(p-chlorobenzene sulphonyl)-3-substituted urea (0.01 mol) and dry chloroform (50 ml) were refluxed for 6 hr. Thereafter, the chloroform was distilled off, the pasty mass, thus obtained, was treated with a solution of potassium carbonate and the resulting mixture containing potassium salt of barbituric acid was filtered. Gradual addition of dil. HCl to the filtrate precipitated the barbituric acid which crystallised from hot water.

The barbituric acids, along with their relevant data are entered in Table 3.

Hypoglycemic evaluation: The test compounds were administered to a group of three fasted albino rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg body weight. The glucose content of the blood drawn from the tail vein at different intervals was estimated by the method of Somogyi¹⁶.

The compounds numbered 2, 4 and 9 (Table 2) decreased the blood sugar, only by 5, 0 and 9% respectively.

Amongst the three barbituric acids screened, the most active was found to be 1-(p chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-3-n propylbarbituric acid which reduced the blood sugar by 33%. The latter was followed by its 3-cyclohexyl and 3-p-methoxyphenyl analogs which caused reduction in blood sugar by 25 and 21% respectively. However, contrary to our expectation, the cyclisation of N¹-(p-chlorobenzenesulphonyl)-N³-substituted ureas to the corresponding barbituric acids did not enhance the hypoglycemic activity.

TABLE-2. 1-(5-ALKYL-1, 3, 4-THIADIAZOL-2-YL)-5-(SUBSTITUTED BENZYLIDENE) HYDANTOINS

S. No.	R	Ar	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Percentage of Nitrogen	
						Found	Calcd.
1.	CH ₃	4-ClC ₆ H ₄	> 300	45	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ SCl	17.00	17.47
2.*	CH ₃	4-(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	> 300	52	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₅ S	21.46	21.28
3.	CH ₃	2-NO ₂ -4, 5-(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	> 300	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₅ S	17.53	17.90
4.*	C ₂ H ₅	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	191	61	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄ SCl	17.02	16.74
5.	C ₂ H ₅	4-(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	170	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₅ S	20.62	20.41
6.	C ₂ H ₅	2-NO ₂ -4, 5-(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	182-3	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₅ S	17.48	17.28
7.	n-C ₃ H ₇	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	206	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ SCl	15.78	16.07
8.	n-C ₃ H ₇	4-(CH ₃) ₂ NC ₆ H ₄	186	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₅ S	19.84	19.61
9.*	n-C ₃ H ₇	2-NO ₂ -4, 5-(CH ₃ O) ₂ C ₆ H ₃	197	69	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₆ N ₅ S	16.69	16.71

*Screened for hypoglycemic activity-see text

TABLE-3. 1-(6-CHLOROBENZENESULPHONYL)-3-(ALKYL/ARYL/CYCLOHEXYL) BARBITURIC ACIDS

S. No.	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Percentage of Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	C ₂ H ₅	160-1	50	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₃ SCl	8.02	8.47
2.*	n-C ₃ H ₇	140	55	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₅ N ₃ SCl	8.46	8.13
3.	n-C ₄ H ₉	125	55	C ₁₄ H ₁₅ O ₅ N ₃ SCl	7.74	7.81
4.*	C ₆ H ₁₁	170	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ O ₅ N ₃ SCl	7.59	7.28
5.	C ₆ H ₅	199	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₅ N ₃ SCl	7.65	7.39
6.	4-Cl C ₆ H ₄	201-3	64	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₃ SCl ₂	6.89	6.78
7.	2-CH ₃ O C ₆ H ₄	148	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₃ SCl	7.11	6.85
8.*	4-CH ₃ O C ₆ H ₄	156	70	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₃ SCl	7.23	6.85

*Screened for hypoglycemic activity-See Text.

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